

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 6.2 1st Midterm Project Dissemination Impact Assessment Report Public

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1. Introduction

This document is part of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation work package - WP6, and it outlines project dissemination activities and the overall key performance indicators (KPIs) reached over the first 1,5 years of the project, as defined in the dissemination and communication plan. The Dissemination Impact will serve as a form of self-evaluation that supports the review of reached KPIs and overall performance of the dissemination efforts.

The document includes the following sections:

- Section 1: Overview of Dissemination Activities
- Section 2: Analysis of Dissemination KPIs
- Section 3: Conclusions and Future Recommendations

2. Overview of Dissemination and Communication Activities

2.1. Summary of Dissemination Activities

The following table shows a short summary of dissemination activities performed during the first reporting period of the project.

Table 1 Summary of Dissemination Activities

No.	Activity	Number of activities	Audience reached/impressions
1	Organised Workshops	4	100
2	Other external workshops attendance	2	70
3	Press Releases (online)	4	>200
4	Policy paper	1	>1000
5	Project Presentations at External Meetings	3	120
6	Flyers Created (various events)	5	-
7	Social Media posts Twitter	48	17964
8	Social Media posts LinkedIn	82	22428
9	Website Posts	27	22881
10	Participation to Conferences/Brokerage events	7	~2000
11	Other Publications	3	~10000
12	Organised Dissemination Events	1	40
13	Organised Joint Live Exercises	1	~30
14	Organised Webinars	1	50
15	Participation to external webinars	1	~50
16	Videos	1	-
17	Leaflets created	3	-
18	External channels used i.e. networks of practitioners, result booster platforms etc.	4	~10000
19	Project cooperation membership (clustering)	20	~200
20	Newsletters	1	-
21	Newsletter subscribers	104	-
22	Established Cooperation with other institutions/agencies	9 out of the 13 contacted	-

2.2. Dissemination Events

Table 2 List of external dissemination events where CYCLOPES has been represented

	Date (DD/MM/YY)	Activity	Event	Location	Attended by	Audience type	Number of participants	Dissemination of / relevance to CYCLOPES
1	16.12.2021	Cyclopes Presentation Workshop	H2020 CONNEXIONS-CREST joint workshop	Online	DITSS, Peter van de Crommert	CONNEXION and CREST consortium partners	+/- 40	Potential Sister Projects and future Cyclopes Community Members
2	23-24.02.2022	Cyclopes presentation at the Meeting	Meetings with EJCN/EUROJUST, Europol Innovation Lab, EC3, European Clearance Board, ENLETS	The Hague, Netherlands	PPHS, HO, CENTRIC, ASI, DITSS, CRI	Representatives of EJCN/EUROJUST, Europol Innovation Lab, EC3, European Clearance Board, ENLETS	in total 15 people	-
3	22.03.2022	Presentation at the conference	CP2 "Fighting cybercrime conference"	Warsaw, Poland	PPHS	LEAs	100	-
4	20.04.2022	Conference/panel discussion	First CYCLOPES dissemination event and panel discussion	Brussels, Belgium	All	LEAs, SMEs, Institutions, other	40-60	Dissemination of results
5	27.04.2022	Webinar	Joint webinar with ECHO and EUHYBNET project and Laurea	Online	DITSS, LAUREA	Networks of practitioners from ECHO and EUHYBNET networks, public, students	40-60	Dissemination of project results

6	10-12.5.2022	JLE	CYCLOPES Joint Live Exercise, Mobile Forensics	UCD, Ireland	PPHS, UCD Swedish Police (Organisers) LEAs from: Belgium The Netherlands Spain Ireland Bulgaria Germany Estonia England, UK Lithuania Portugal UK Wales, UK Poland Sweden (Practitioners)	Practitioners	30	Introduction to solutions
7	16-17.5.2022	Participation to panel discussion/brokerage event	SMI2G2022 Brokerage event	Brussels	PPHS			Dissemination of project results/experiences
8	24.05.2022	Webinar	CYCLOPES webinar	Online	DITSS, PPHS, LEICESTERSHIRE POLICE, TNO, HOME OFFICE UK.	Public	40-60	Dissemination/discussion on project results related to Social Engineering.
9	09.06.2022	Conference participation	EEMA2022 Annual Conference	Microsoft HQ,	PPHS	Public	200	Insights into tech development regarding digital

				London, UK				forensics, e-identity, e-privacy, cybersecurity and others.
10	09.06.2022	Presentation at the conference	Law Enforcement for the Digital Age, European Research & Science Conference”	Vilnius, Lithuania	PPHS	LEAs, Other	200	Results dissemination
11	30.5.-03.06.2022	CYCLOPES exhibition participant	EAFS2022	Stockholm, Sweden	LAUREA, DITSS, UCD	SMEs, LEAs	1000	Potential LEAs interested in collaboration and joining the network
12	30.5.-03.06.2022	CYCLOPES workshop/info session	EAFS2022	Stockholm, Sweden	LAUREA, DITSS, UCD	SMEs, LEAs	(+/-)30	-
13	30.5.-03.06.2022	CYCLOPES presentation of Policy paper	EAFS2022	Stockholm, Sweden	DITSS, Peter van de Crommert		1000	-
	30.06 – 01.07 2022	CERIS Event	Project to Policy Seminar	Brussels, Belgium	PPHS	Research and Policy	100	Dissemination
15	20.7.2022	Digital Investigation Advisory Group (meeting)	Cryptocurrency activity for WP3	Ryton, UK	College of Policing	Digital Investigator Practitioners from across UK	60	Community
16	19.09.2022	Cyber Digital Conference	Cryptocurrency activity for WP3	Sheffield, UK	College of Policing	UK Policing and Law Enforcement	120	Community

17	01.09.2022	Presentation at meeting	ENLETS NCP Meeting	Czech Republic	PPHS	EU Law Enforcement	45	Community of LEAs that are interested and can support CYCLOPES' actions with participation in events and workshops
18	13.09.2022	Networking	EU Innovation Hub Annul Event	Brussels, Belgium	PPHS	Research and Law Enforcement, EU Agencies	60	Community Building and Strengthening
19	27-28.09.2022	Networking	CERIS Community Event	Brussels, Belgium	PPHS	Research and Law Enforcement	60	Community Building and Strengthening
20	29.09.2022	Dissemination	EUROPOL Innovation Lab	The Hague, Netherlands	PPHS	EU Innovation Lab Team (part)	4	Dissemination and Stakeholder Relations

2.3. Dissemination materials, channels and related statistics

Website stats

From M3 onwards, CYCLOPES established its website which serves as the primary channel to support communication and dissemination of project information and results.

The website is accessible from desktop as well as mobile devices on the following address <https://cyclopes-project.eu>. It hosts publicly available content produced by the project such as relevant upcoming events, news, public deliverables, project information, network information and so on.

During the period 01.03.2022 – 31.10.2022 (8 months), the project website has had the following results:

The website has been visited by 1440 users, Served 2380 sessions with over 5600 page views (Figure 1). A session in this case represents the time from the moment a person accesses the CYCLOPES website in the browser until the browser is closed or inactive for 30 minutes. Page views are counted as a total amount of views of all pages during such sessions.

Most page visitors by country:

Page title and screen class	↓ Views	Users	Views per user	Average engagement time	Event count	Con
	5,872 100% of total	1,440 100% of total	4.08 Avg 0%	1m 00s Avg 0%	14,281 100% of total	All e
1 Home - CYCLOPES Project	1,388	618	2.25	0m 24s	4,157	
2 Strona główna - CYLOPES Project	642	243	2.64	0m 32s	1,527	

Figure 1 Overall website audience analytics

Country	↓ Users
	1,440 100% of total
1 United States	274
2 United Kingdom	165
3 Netherlands	120
4 Poland	112
5 Finland	96
6 China	89
7 Germany	72
8 France	55
9 Spain	40
10 Belgium	38

Figure 2 Overall audience of the website by country

Figure 4 Leaflets and poster in display at EAFS22 Conference in Stockholm, Sweden.

Poster

A CYCLOPES network poster has been created (Figure 5) in collaboration with WP5 to be used in the EAFS22 conference as well as other events in the future. The poster has been displayed during the event for one week along with other materials (Figure 4). The poster contains similar information as the network leaflet except in a more graphical representation.

Figure 5 Cyclopes network poster

Roll-ups

The CYCLOPES Roll-up is one of the main materials designed to catch the attention of potential audiences especially when the audience is able to physically or digitally see them (Figure 6).

Figure 6 CYCLOPES roll-ups

LAUREA and PPHS have jointly contributed towards the printing and sending copies to all partners for dissemination purposes.

The roll-up has been displayed in several meetings, conferences, workshops and other events (Figure 7).

Figure 7 CYCLOPES roll-ups on display at EAFS22 conference in Stockholm, Sweden.

Flyers/Banners

For each CYCLOPES organised event such as joint live exercise, workshop or webinar, there was a flyer designed and published in all dissemination channels (Figure 8).

One banner is also created for the social media. This one displays a QR code that directs visitors to the network registration link in the project website (Figure 9).

Figure 8 CYCLOPES flyers dedicated to various events

Figure 9 CYCLOPES social media banner

Video

A video is created in order to promote the first project webinar (Figure 10). More videos are expected to be designed in the future.

Figure 10 Video promoting the first CYCLOPES webinar

Social media and stats

As we have seen through experience, social media platforms offer a great opportunity to target desired audiences to keep them updated with project progress. Their simplicity in publishing content and their openness offers an easy way to reach audiences regardless of the device. The WP6 leader and the project coordinator have decided that for our specific project needs, LinkedIn and Twitter accounts would be more favourable as opposed to Facebook, Instagram and other platforms.

LinkedIn

The project dissemination team has dedicated a significant effort in reaching the targeted audiences via the social media platform. All public information has been shared regularly from the project including important sources of information from relevant clusters, partners and stakeholders.

Worth to note that the LinkedIn page has been actively used only after the first six months of the project. During this time the following statistics have been observed:

In total the project has created 82 LinkedIn posts of which had a combined impression stat of 22,428 as of 25.10.2022.

The follower count has been continuously increasing on average 25 followers per month. Currently there are 305 followers.

Twitter

In similar fashion as the LinkedIn account, a Twitter account has been created for the CYCLOPES project called project-cyclopes. Here too information has been shared regularly as on other channels however, Twitter has been a little less impactful in amassing followers compared to the LinkedIn with only 106 followers at the time of writing this report.

During the reporting period, the project has created a total of 48 posts which yielded a combined impressions stat of 17,964. Despite the significant lower number of posts compared to LinkedIn, it is still an impressive reach.

Dissemination event

On the 20th of April 2022 the 1st CYCLOPES Dissemination Event was held in Brussels, Belgium to present the main project findings to a large spectrum of stakeholders and ensure efficient cooperation between CYCLOPES and relevant partners. The audience was made up of around 40 people from CYCLOPES consortium, LEAs across Europe and representatives from the following networks and organisations engaged in the fight against cybercrime in Europe.

Publications

Table 3 List of all project articles and publications in various channels

	Date (DD/MM/YY)	Author(s)	Title of Publication	Publisher	Link	Partner	Peer reviewed	Open access
	08.12.2021	LAUREA	Press release	LAUREA	-	LAUREA	Yes	Yes
	12.01.2022	LAUREA	Press Release / Finnish	LAUREA	Laurea public website	LAUREA	Yes	Yes
	14.03.2022	LAUREA	Project Newsletter	LAUREA	Link to newsletter	LAUREA		Yes
	25.05.2022	ZITiS	Foresight - Digital Forensics	ZITiS, (LAUREA design)	Link to official publication	ZITiS	Yes	Yes
	16.05.2022	PPHS	1st CYCLOPES Dissemination Event Summary	PPHS	Link to publication	PPHS		Yes
	06.06.2022	PPHS	Year In Review: The Road To Exercises For Mobile Forensic Tools	PPHS, (LAUREA design)	Link to the official publication	PPHS	Yes	Yes
	29.07.2022	TNO	Intermediate results Market Watch	Europol	Dark Web and OSINT tools - Forum - EC3 - SPACE - EPE (europa.eu)	TNO	No	Yes
	09.09.2022	PPHS	CYCLOPES/FORMOBILE Training for Judicial Authorities Call for Review	PPHS	(Leaflet sent via e-mail)	PPHS	Yes	N/A

Newsletters

The official CYCLOPES website has a dedicated space where visitors can subscribe to the newsletter. The form is connected to the SendinBlue service which hosts the newsletter templates and acts as a mailing platform.

The newsletter (Figure 11) is dedicated to the wider audience with the aim to inform on latest project activities, planned events and any future work.

As of 25.10.2022 there are 104 newsletter subscribers on the database. One newsletter has been delivered and the next one is scheduled to be delivered in November 2022. In addition to the SendInblue platform, the newsletter is also shared in all other project channels.

Figure 11 CYCLOPES Newsletter

Press Releases

These types of publications have been shared with the wide audience before the project started as well as afterwards. Since the project did not have a dedicated website, these types of publications have been shared in own organisations' websites (Figure 12).

CYCLOPES – Hanke, jolla luodaan innovointiin perustuva kyberrikollisuutta torjuvien lainvalvontaviranomaisten verkosto

Laurean vastualueeseen kuuluvat hankkeen viestintä ja verkoston rakentaminen sekä kyberrikollisuuden torjuntaan liittyviä tutkimustoimia.

Lutinen **20.12.2021**

Figure 12 CYCLOPES press release published in Laurea's webpage

As of the time of reporting, There are two official press releases shared. One in English and one in Finnish language. Both have been shared in Laurea’s website and social media. There are also two other unofficial press releases shared on Laurea’s website before the project started.

Public versions of restricted reports

It was decided that due to the nature of the project deliverables being mostly restricted and as such unable to share with the public, we would put an effort into creating shortened public versions of such deliverables and reports with an appealing design in order to maximise the impact of the project towards the targeted audiences.

Thus far there have been three such publications delivered across all CYCLOPES channels. More of them are in the process. Such reports include but are not limited to: Workshop results, policy briefs, joint live exercise reports and selected deliverables (Figure 13).

Figure 13 Shortened public versions of restricted reports

Network members

Dissemination towards increasing the network membership has been promoted and ongoing throughout the majority of dissemination events, materials and channels. Currently these calls are ongoing on project’s social media, website, newsletters, leaflets, poster and so on.

Requests for membership can be made via the project’s website <https://www.cyclopes-project.eu/join-us>

Currently there are 53 Individual members in the CYCLOPES network representing more than 38 different organisations.

Organised Webinars

The CYCLOPES project organises webinars annually. On the 24th of May 2022, the 1st CYCLOPES webinar was held online. The event was organised and hosted by the Dutch

Institute for Technology, Safety and Security (DITSS). The audience was made up of around 45 participants from LEAs across Europe.

Participation to other webinars

During the reporting period the CYCLOPES project has participated to at least one external webinar, where it presented the current results at the time. The audience in that webinar has been more than 50 persons (Figure 14).

Figure 14 Webinar held at Laurea

External Dissemination Platforms

All results and public information is being actively shared in various platforms where CYCLOPES stakeholders may be reached. Most of these platforms are offered by European Commission and other EU LEA organisations.

The European Network of Law Enforcement Technology Services (ENLETS) ¹

The project has started using the ENLETS messaging system for its network members and sharing results with the already 322 LEA members as at the time of writing the report.

EU CIRCABC ²

CIRCABC platform is a space offered by European Union with the main aim to support information sharing and collaboration between various networks of practitioners. Currently, CYCLOPES is sharing information with over 50 NoPs, with two representatives as POC from each.

Europol Platform for Exports Forum ³

¹ <https://enlets.eu/>

² <https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/welcome>

³ https://sts.europol.europa.eu/adfs/oauth2/authorize?scope=openid+email+profile&response_type=code&redirect_uri=https%3A%2F%2Ffepe.europol.europa.eu%2F%2Fportal%2Flogin%2Fopenidconnect&state=k0Zx5zloXefRF_Z05IQrpLIUCEldc08M-JdsHHop4EM&nonce=m7tuv8fZ3AUucA3G-pcWcNj8skJL79i_fz1Tk49inw4&client_id=PRD_EPE_ServerApp

The SPACE subgroup has 8000 members, and so far more than 40 LEA representatives have requested access to our intermediate results.

Collaboration with other projects/networks

CC-Driver LEA Cluster

Since month around March 2022 the project has officially joined the CC-Driver LEA cluster (Figure 15) of over 20 projects that share similar objectives and stakeholders.

The overall objective of the cluster is the following:

1. To share knowledge in order to support law enforcement against money-laundering, cybercrime, organised crime and terrorism, for example, by webinars for the partners in the cluster.
2. To leverage our dissemination activities by mentioning the projects in the cluster on our websites, inviting articles from the cluster projects in our newsletter.
3. To ensure the coherence and complementarity of our recommendations to the EC, LEAs and other stakeholders, as far as possible.
4. To explore a degree of interoperability or compatibility between our technical platforms, modules and/or services.
5. To explore synergies, research opportunities and possible joint exploitation activities.

Figure 15 CC-Driver LEA cluster

CERIS Community

The CYCLOPES project has attended several CERIS events during 2022 and has engaged directly with relevant projects and stakeholders from across Europe – informing them an updating them on related actions and activities. Although the project has not had a formal presentation – the awareness-raising is a useful tool to inform appropriate members of the research community about the tasks CYCLOPES is working on.

Established Cooperation Partnerships

The CYCLOPES project during the first reporting period has contacted thirteen different organisations and established cooperation with the following:

- EUROPOL Innovation Lab,

- EUROPOL EC3 (European Cybercrime Centre),
- European Judicial Cybercrime Network,
- ENLETS,
- European Clearing Board,
- EACTDA,
- EMPACT,
- EU Commission

3. Dissemination KPIs Analysis

During the first year of the project, the dissemination plan was created. The plan defined the tools for measuring the success of dissemination efforts in different stages of the project. These guidelines include a set of KPIs which were created by the WP6 leader in cooperation with the project coordinator. The KPIs help us to understand the direction the project is going by defining requirements in several steps of dissemination and support us to understand what corrective measures are necessary for the future. These KPIs are to be reviewed at several intervals during the lifetime of the project (Table 4).

In order to measure the performance of the KPIs, a colour scheme has been chosen each determining the level of performance:

- Green – The KPI is met or exceeded
- Yellow – The KPI has met the average level and there is room for improvement
- Grey – The KPI has met the low level of expectation and improvements are recommended

Table 4 Dissemination KPI analysis

Target					
KPIs		Level of performance			Remarks
D&C Tools	Definition of indicator	Poor	Good	Excellent	
Project Website	The number of visits	Less than 140 per month	140-300 per month	more than 300 per month	The website has served 2380 sessions over the course of 8 months.
	The number of page views	Less than 300 per month	300-500 per month	more than 500 per month	The website has over 5600 page views during

					the course of 8 months.
	Average time spent on website	Less than 30 sec.	30 sec. – 1:30 min.	more than 1.5 min.	The average time spent on the website is 1:00 min.
Social Media	Followers on LinkedIn	Less than 50 per year	80 on yearly basis	More than 80 on yearly basis	There are over 300 followers on the 1,5 years.
	Followers on Twitter	Less than 60 per year	90 on yearly basis	more than 90 on yearly basis	For the first year there have been 106 Followers. It is rather slow hence might need adjustment in the future.
	Number of posts	Less than 3 per month	3-7 per month	More than 7 per month	There have been over 80 posts during the year. on LKDIN and over 40 on Twitter.
Annual Joint Live Exercises	Number of practitioners per event	Less than 3 per event	20-25 per event	More than 25 per event	
	Number of participants form the scientific community per event	Less than 7 (online) Less than 5 (physical)	7-10 (online) 5-7(physical)	More than 10 (online) More than 7 (physical)	
	Number of participants from the Industry/SME per event	less than 2 per event	2-3 per event	More than 3per event	

Annual Dissemination Event	Number of participants per event	less than 70 per event	70-100 per event	more than 100 per event	There were around 40 participants.
Annual Standardisation Workshop	Number of participants per event	less than 70 per event	70-100 per event	more than 100 per event	No data was available at the time of writing the deliverable
Practitioner Workshops	Number of participants per workshop	Less than 10 (online) Less than 7 (physical)	10-15 (Online) 7-12 (physical)	More than 15 (online) More than 12 (physical)	There have been on average 15-20 participants per event and due to logistical reasons many more had to be refused participation.
Participation to External Events	Number of external events in which CYCLOPES participates	less than 5 per year	5-10 per year	more than 10 per year	There have been 16 different events noted with 10 of them being external.
Liaison Activities and Synergies	Number of relevant projects/initiatives identified and contacted/invited at project events	Less than 4 on yearly basis	4-12 on yearly basis	more than 12 on yearly basis	Over 50 NoP have been contacted and invited to the project events.
	Number of relevant organisations/communities/experts identified and contacted/invited at project events	less than 12 on yearly basis	12-30 on a yearly basis	More than 30 on a yearly basis	There have been over 13 organisations that have been contacted to establish cooperation.
	Number of cooperation activities (common events and other clustering activities)	less than 1 on a yearly basis	2-3 on a yearly basis	more than 3 on a yearly basis	There have been at least three different occasions where

					project has been represented.
Link to the Community of Users	Number of 'CYCLOPES' presentations made during plenary meetings and thematic workshops	1 per year	2 per year	more than 2 per year	
Webinars	participants to the webinars	20-29 per webinar or less	30-49 per webinar	50 or more per webinar	There have been 50 participants to the last webinar.
Bi-Annual Newsletters	Newsletters published	Less than 2 per year	2 per year	more than 2 per year	One newsletter has been written thus far and a second one is planned for next month.
	Subscribers	20-50	50-100	more than 100	Currently there are 104 Newsletter subscribers.
CYCLOPES Community of Users	Number of new members (organisations not individuals)	0-10 per year	10-20 per year	more than 20 per year	Currently there are approx. 38 confirmed members.

4. Conclusion and future recommendations

Despite having a slow start for the first six months, the project has been quite successful in reaching the targeted audiences during the reporting period. All public information has been shared to various forums and platforms where targeted audiences may be reached. Especially the LEA community is well reached, however there is still room for improvement in reaching I.e. the Industry and policymakers.

The initiative to produce shortened public versions of classified reports has been received well. From now on it is seen as a good practice to continue this way. The number of these reports will be increased from events based to also include other deliverables. The relevant channels will also be more diversified to include other stakeholders from the industry and policymaking.

The website has almost reached the green indicator when it comes to set session targets per month. The session data shows only 20 sessions lower than the expected 2400. We expect in the future this will be relatively higher especially with the increased activity online and the engagement with the LEA clusters, other NoP and dissemination of deliverables to various other channels.

Workshops and other events organised had relatively short time intervals between one another yet managed to receive satisfactory participation from relevant stakeholders. It is planned that these intervals will be significantly longer in the future.

After the six months period, it is noticed that the project dissemination has started to be more impactful. There is already a base of regular participants established and is being filled with new ones as time progresses.

The extended cooperation with other networks and organisations has been largely successful and the project sees that this trend will be increasing.

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